

Supplementary Material 1

Inter-annual electricity balancing in 100% renewable energy systems assessed through a techno-economic comparison of data series length, e-hydrogen versus e-methane, and multi-objective solutions

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Note 1: Methodology for ERA5 full load hour calculation

The primary weather data used for this study's long-term analysis is the ERA5 reanalysis dataset, covering the 85-year period from 1940 to 2024 [1]. Due to the high computational requirements of processing global, high-resolution data for this extended period, a representative sampling approach was used for the 14 selected regions. The aim of this approach was to derive a regional full load hour (FLH) profile that reasonably approximates the aggregated average of the entire region, thereby reducing the risk of data variance that could arise from using a single coordinate.

For each of the 14 representative regions, five specific latitude and longitude points were selected. These points were hand-picked to be representative of the region's resource mix, using the aggregated average regional FLH for the year 2005 from the full 400x800 resolution NASA dataset as a benchmark. The hourly weather data (including solar irradiance and wind speeds at relevant altitudes) was then extracted from the ERA5 dataset for these five points for the entire 85-year time series.

The solar photovoltaics (PV) and wind power FLH were then calculated for each individual point using the LUT-PV model [2] and the wind power model from Satymov et al. [3], respectively. To create a single, representative time series for each of the 14 regions, the hourly FLH values from the five selected points were arithmetically averaged. This mean FLH time series was then used as the primary input for the inter-annual storage (IAS) optimisation model for all ERA5 scenarios.

Note 2: Direct comparison of NASA and ERA5 datasets (1984–2005)

To isolate the impact of the reanalysis models', i.e., NASA [4–6] and ERA5, intrinsic characteristics from the effect of the different time-series lengths, a direct comparison was conducted for the concurrent 22-year period from 1984 to 2005.

Resource variability comparison

The analysis first compares the statistical properties of the VRE resources derived from the NASA and ERA5 datasets over the same 1984-2005 timeframe to isolate the intrinsic differences between the reanalysis models. Figure S1 shows the deviation from the median annual FLH for solar PV, wind power, and the capacity-weighted average FLH for the 14 representative regions. Negative deviations are particularly important, as these represent the deficit years that drive the need for storage and overcapacity, and thus determine the system cost.

For wind power, both the NASA and ERA5 datasets show significant inter-annual variability (IAV), but they identify different extreme years. The NASA dataset presents a more severe deficit profile in several key regions, most notably in Indonesia (ID-JV+TL) with a -33% deviation and Kenya and Uganda (KENUG) with a -23% deviation. Although ERA5 data shows a slightly wider overall range of variability in some regions like Great Britain & Ireland (BRI), its negative outliers are consistently less extreme for this period, with KENUG at -10% and Southeast Brazil (BR-SE) at -11%.

This pattern continues for solar PV, which has inherently lower inter-annual variability. The most extreme negative deviation across all regions and both datasets is again found in the NASA data for Southeast Brazil (BR-SE), which shows a worst-year deficit of -11%. In contrast, the largest negative deviation in the ERA5 data for the same period is a slightly lower -10% for the same region.

These individual resource characteristics culminate in the capacity-weighted FLH profiles. This integrated metric reveals that for the concurrent 1984-2005 period, the intrinsic properties of the NASA dataset create a more demanding scenario for system balancing in several key regions. This is crucial for interpreting the subsequent techno-economic results, as it demonstrates that the higher system requirements found when using the full 85-year ERA5 dataset are not an artefact of the ERA5 model being inherently more expensive. Instead, it confirms that the primary driver for the increased system costs is indeed the extended time

series capturing a wider and more challenging range of low-frequency climate events.

Figure S1. Comparison of annual FLH deviation from the median for solar PV (top) and wind power (bottom) across the 14 representative regions for the concurrent 1984-2005 period, derived from the NASA and ERA5 datasets. Please refer to Table 2 of the main article for the region definition.

The intrinsic differences in the resource profiles of the two datasets, as detailed in the previous subsection, directly translate into different optimal system designs, even when analysed over the same 22-year period. Figure S2 presents a direct comparison of the key system requirements for the minimum curtailment solution in the e-H₂ scenario, comparing the outcomes derived from the NASA and ERA5 datasets for the 1984-2005 period.

The results reveal a counter-intuitive finding that for this specific historical period, planning with the ERA5 dataset leads to a less demanding and more cost-effective system design for most of the 14 representative regions compared to the NASA dataset. This is observed across all three key metrics. The required VRE overcapacity is lower in 11 of the 14 regions when using ERA5 data, with the demand-weighted average showing a 14.8% reduction. This trend is even more pronounced for the physical storage requirements, where the demand-weighted average for IAS capacity is 15.1% lower with the ERA5 data.

This reduction in physical infrastructure requirements translates directly into lower costs. The ACOIAS is also lower in most regions when using the ERA5 data for this period, with a global demand-weighted average reduction of 15.0%. The most significant cost reductions are seen

in regions like Iberia (IBE), California (US-CA), and North China (CN-N), with decreases of over 40%. Whereas in Germany (DE) the ERA5 dataset leads to a substantially more costly system in this direct comparison, with an increase of over 70% in ACOIAS.

This analysis strongly supports the conclusion that the intrinsic characteristics of the NASA reanalysis model, which contains more negative outlier years for variable renewable electricity generation within the 1984-2005 period, create a more challenging environment for system optimisation than the ERA5 data for the same period. This confirms that the dramatic increase in system costs documented in the main paper is overwhelmingly driven by the extended 85-year length of the ERA5 dataset capturing more extreme long-term climate variability, rather than by any inherent pessimism in the ERA5 model itself.

Figure S2. Comparison of minimum curtailment system requirements for the e-H₂ scenario using NASA vs ERA5 data for the concurrent 1984-2005 period. Required VRE overcapacity (top), required IAS capacity (centre), and annualised cost of the IAS system (ACOIAS) (bottom). The bar plots on the left of each pair show the absolute value, and the bar plots on

the right of each pair show the relative percentage change when moving from the NASA to the ERA dataset. Please refer to Table 2 of the main article for the region definition.

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